

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERACTIVE GAMES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES PROCESS.

Rokhila Bafoeva

Teacher of Asia International University

bafoyevarohila@oxu.uz

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Abstract. In recent years, the focus on the matter of the study and teaching of foreign languages has increased significantly. Nowadays, teaching any foreign language without appropriate and innovative methods, techniques, interactive activities and games is quite challenging for language learners and teachers. Implying these kinds of games during the lesson increase learners' interest and attention to learn other languages. In this article the author discussed several games which are planned to teach foreign languages for the students with different knowledge background and age.

Keywords. Games, methods, foreign language, activities, learners, teachers, classroom environment, knowledge background, tactics, role playing, board race, object.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ИГР В ПРОЦЕССЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ.

Аннотация. В последние годы внимание к вопросу изучения и преподавания иностранных языков значительно возросло. В настоящее время преподавание любого иностранного языка без соответствующих и инновационных методов, техник, интерактивных занятий и игр является довольно сложной задачей для изучающих язык и учителей. Использование подобных игр во время урока повышает интерес и внимание обучающихся к изучению других языков. В этой статье автор рассмотрел несколько игр, которые планируется использовать для обучения иностранным языкам учащихся с разным уровнем знаний и возраста.

Ключевые слова. Игры, методы, иностранный язык, занятия, уроки, учителя, классная среда, фон знаний, тактика, ролевая игра, гонка за доской, предмет.

Introduction. Learning foreign languages has an importance role in developing period of the world. In this case, languages are taught not only in higher education institutions, schools, but also in pre-school educational institutions. If it is not taught with interesting methods and activities, but traditional methods during the class, it can be difficult to attract students to the lesson. Implying distinct methods in the lesson not only ensures the quality of the lesson, but at the same time prevents boredom and attracts passive students to participate in the lesson.

Materials and methods. There are a number of various interesting games in the process of teaching English and Russian. That is worth mentioning that when teaching any age level learners, it is necessary to use such games, let all students participate equally in them and get something useful from the lesson (for instance, new vocabulary can be memorized, if this process is repeated every day, the student's vocabulary increases to a higher level).

A lesson for students it is inappropriate to start with grammatical concepts, especially for students of lower grades or level. It causes boredom quickly. As a result, interest in education may fade. Even the process of greeting with them should be started in an extraordinary way, including,

an English song about a kind of greeting to the class when the teacher enters starting with (mainly a motivational method for elementary school students) method is an effective method. If the lesson continues in this way, the students do not lose their attention to the task. They even wait next English class eagerly. Of course, all this is done by the teacher who is a main organizer and it requires the pedagogue's responsibility. Some types of games can be mentioned to make learning foreign language as interesting as.

Result and discussion. "Role playing" activity improves the effectiveness of English and Russian language lessons. The advantage of this game is that it comes from the situation which will be played. This game is not only useful for learning science, but also it also helps to build intellectual skills. In this game, the topics are selected and students create dialogues. For example, the situational conversation of a passenger who stopped a taxi, or conversations in clothing stores, at the airport and others.

Students will act and speak in English according to their situation. In this activity, learners work with a group or a partner. Also, this help students to collaborate in different cases. Furthermore, there will be a sense of competitiveness by dividing students into groups and different topics. In this case, competition occurs. Competition is the criterion of improvement. Finally, teachers should not forget to reward students or groups who participated in this activity well. It is also appropriate to use didactic games to achieve a meaningful learning process.

“Board Race” ESL game is an exciting way to get the whole class up and out of their seat. This activity can be used with any age and level students as well as adults, based on the classroom size. Students should be aware how to pronounce the letters of alphabet. When the teacher spell the letters of a word(for instance, s-m-a-l-l), two students should come to the board with their markers or chock to write down the word spelled by the teacher. This activity can be used in order to revise the vocabulary given as homework or as a warm-up activity at the beginning part of the lesson.

“Object” ESL game serves to provide vocabulary for students. As we know, the most important direction in learning a foreign language is to learn new words. If we observe the characters of the students, each student has his own way to learn and memorize vocabularies. Learning new words through games is an appropriate way for everyone and it simplifies the process. Several objects are placed on the table in the classroom and students come and inspect these items. Items are covered and then students will write the objects which they have already seen. The student who can write many words correctly will be the winner.

Conclusion. In general, on the basis of learning foreign languages process should be conducted with the help of interactive games and activities in order to achieve reproductive results While using games during the lesson, teachers should choose them according to learners knowledge background and age. These games can be changed in order to make it easier or more complicated. The purpose of the mentioned games is to strengthen the students' memory, intellectual capacity, quickness, intelligence, and organize the lesson meaningfully.

REFERENCES

1. Brandvik, M. L., & McKnight, K. S. The English Teacher's Survival Guide: Ready To-Use Techniques and Materials for Grades 7-12. Jossey-Bass. [4]
2. Sandford R, Ulicsak M, Facer K and Rudd T “ Using commercial off-the-shelf computer games in formal education.” Retrived 28-10-2011 from < http://www2.futurelab.org.uk/resources/documents/project_reports/teaching_with_games/TWG_report.pdf>, 2005. [5]
3. Pirmanovna, N. G., & Bafoeva, R. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROVERBS. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(4), 227-230.
4. Hayles, N. K. “Electronic Literature: New Horizons for the Literary” . Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame Press, 2008. [7] Hayes, R. T. “The Effectiveness of Instructional Games”. Naval Air Warfare Center, Orlando, (November 2005). [8]
5. Bafoeva, R. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK MAQOLLARINING SHAKLLANISH VA O'RGANILISH MASALALARI. Научный Фокус, 1(3), 29-31.
6. Артамонова Л.Н. Игры на уроке Английского языка и во внеклассной работы. // Английский язык, №4, 2008 – с.363. Петрова Л.В. Игровые технологии на уроках английского языка// Английский язык, №11, 2008 – с.5 : с илл. [10] Выготский Л.С. Игра и ее роль в психологическом развитии ребенка // Вопросы психологии. – 1966. – с.45
7. Jabborova, A. (2023). WHAT IS DESIGN THINKING?. *Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar*, 1(13). извлечено от <http://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/941>
8. Голышкина И.В., Ефанова. З.А. Изучаем английский играя / авт.-сост.- Волгоград: Учитель, 2007. – 128 с.
9. Калимулина, О. В. Ролевые игры в обучении диалогической речи / О. В. Калимулина // Иностранные языки в школе. – 2003. - № 3. – С. 17-20. 9. [13] Колесникова О.А. Ролевые игры в обучении иностранным языкам. // Иностранные языки в школе. – 1989. - №4. с 73-80
10. Jabborova, A. (2023). THE IMPACTS OF PHYSICAL CLASSROOM SPACES ON STUDENTS INVOLVEMENT HOW CAN STUDENTS ENGAGEMENT BE PROMOTED BY PHYSICAL CLASSROOM SPACES?. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(3), 115-121.